

FRACTURE ANALYSIS OF MIXED-MODE FAILURE PROCESSES
IN A 3D-FIBRE/MATRIX COMPOSITE CYLINDER

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ABSTRACT

The straightforward and highly effective numerical procedure of the improved modified crack closure integral method is generalized for covering non-plane crack problems with axial symmetry and non-coplanar crack extension in a 3D-composite cylinder. For this circular fibre/matrix composite cylinder of finite dimensions the fibre pullout problem is considered for a uniaxial tensile loading of the fibre and different boundary conditions of fibre and matrix. Furthermore two thermally induced fibre/matrix debonding processes are analysed by means of the generalized method, including different mixed-mode conditions at the crack fronts, respectively. Modes I and II are involved if the circular interface crack extends in the axial direction of the compound cylinder, whereas modes I, II and III occur with interface crack extension in the circumferential direction.

INTRODUCTION

Parts of aircraft or spacecraft structures manufactured from composite materials often are subjected to superimposed mechanical and thermal loadings during service. Both kinds of loadings may cause fracture and failure of composite structures and that is why the fracture analysis of mechanically and/or thermally stressed composite materials are important subjects in today's material- and engineering sciences /1-4/.

The number of analytical solutions in this field is limited /2,3,5/ because not only geometric and material discontinuities have to be considered, but in general mixed-mode fracture problems occur if a crack extends in dissimilar isotropic or anisotropic materials /4,5,3/. Furthermore many analytical results and numerical methods, well established in the fracture analysis of homogeneous isotropic materials are not always applicable to typical fracture processes in composite materials /2,6/. One of the exceptions is the very straightforward and numerically highly effective procedure of the improved modified crack closure integral method /4,7/.

In this paper it is shown that the method can be generalized to non-plane crack problems with axial symmetry and to 3D-problems with non-coplanar crack extension. This is done by the fracture analysis of a circular fibre/matrix composite cylinder of finite diameter and length (Figs. 3,16 and Table 1). Divergent from results given in /8/ it is shown that the

mechanically created fibre pullout generates mixed-mode I and II conditions at the circular crack front, extending in axial direction along the fibre/matrix interface. This problem is considered with different boundary conditions of fibre and matrix (Fig. 1) and with thermal stresses created by a homogeneous temperature rise $\Delta T = \text{const.}$ of the compound cylinder.

TABLE 1

Thermoelastic Parameters				Mechanical Parameters			
		Fibre SiC	Matrix Al			Fibre SiC	Matrix Al
Young's mod.	$E(\text{N/mm}^2)$	449.300	69.650	Radius	$r(\text{mm})$	5.477	10
Poisson's rat.	$\nu(1)$	0.226	0.339	Height	$H(\text{mm})$	10	10
Linear CTE	$\alpha(1/^\circ\text{C})$	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	Vol. Fract.	$V_f/V(\%)$	30	
Temperatur	$\Delta T(^\circ\text{C})$	100	100	Load	$F(\text{N})$	1000	

Furthermore a thermally induced debonding process as shown in Fig. 16 is analysed. It will be seen that this non-coplanar crack extension generates highly mixed-mode I, II and III conditions at the crack front, with an increasing and predominating mode III-term near to the top surface of the cylinder. For the thermoelastic cases under consideration the accuracy of the method is proved quantitatively on the basis of the elastic strain energy ensued in the uncracked composite cylinder.

GLOBAL ENERGY METHOD

According to IRWIN /9/ for an elastic solid or structure containing a crack the change of the total potential $\Pi(a)$ due to a crack extension from length a to $a+\Delta a$ is equal to the correlated total energy release rate $G(a)$. This relation

$$G(a) = \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Pi(a+\Delta a) - \Pi(a)}{t\Delta a} = \frac{d\Pi(a)}{tda} \quad (1)$$

(t thickness of plane structure), has the disadvantage that the separated energy release rates $G_i(a)$, $i=I,II,III$ can not be extracted from it, although they are of most importance for the fracture analysis of composite materials in which mixed-mode crack tip conditions arise in general. Nevertheless the global energy method (EN-method, Eq. (1)) can be very useful for checking the accuracy of other methods delivering the $G_i(a)$ -values by different approaches (local energy methods for example). But this provides that the numerical differentiation involved in Eq. (1) is not simply performed by $\Delta\Pi/\Delta a$ but in an appropriate way. The total potential $\Pi(a)$ is given by

$$\Pi(a) = W(a) - U(a) \quad (2)$$

with

$$W(a) = \underline{r}^T \underline{R} \quad (3)$$

and

$$U(a) = \frac{1}{2} \underline{r}^T(a) \underline{K}(a) \underline{r}(a) \quad (4)$$

denoting the work done by the applied mechanical loads and the elastic strain energy of the structure, respectively (\underline{r} displacement vector, \underline{R} load vector, \underline{K} stiffness matrix of the structure). In case of thermal loads \underline{r} has to be replaced in Eq. (4) by the effective displacement vector

$$\underline{r}_e(a) = \underline{r}_a(a) - \underline{r}_0 \tag{5}$$

considering that only the difference of the actual displacements $\underline{r}_a(a)$ and \underline{r}_0 , which denotes the unrestricted (stress free) displacements due to thermal loads, are defining $U(a)$ then /10/.

CRACK CLOSURE INTEGRAL METHOD

Referring to Fig. 1 and its notations for a pure mode I condition one can write in accordance with IRWIN /9/ the following well known crack closure integral relation

$$G_I(a) = \lim_{\delta a \rightarrow 0} \frac{2}{\delta a} \int_{x=0}^{x=\delta a} \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{yy}(r=x, \phi=0, a) u_y(r=\delta a-x, \phi=\pi, a+\delta a) dx. \tag{6}$$

Equation (6) states, that the energy release rate for collinear crack extension by δa is equal to the work which has to be done by the stresses $\sigma_{yy}(, a)$ at the crack face displacements $u_y(, a+\delta a)$ (dashed line in Fig. 1) in order to close the crack by δa to its original length a again ($G_I(a) \equiv G(a)$ for pure mode I).

Fig.1 Crack closure integral method (analytical)

Fig.2 Crack closure integral method (numerical), 2C- and L2-method

According to BUCHHOLZ et al and KANNINEN /4,7,10,11/ Eq.(6) can be transformed into an equivalent FE-representation

$$G_I(a+\Delta a/2) = \frac{1}{t} \frac{1}{2\Delta a} (F_{y,i}(a) \Delta u_{y,i-2}(a+\Delta a) + F_{y,i+1}(a) \Delta u_{y,i-1}(a+\Delta a)) \tag{7}$$

which is valid in combination with a linear strain element (LSE) discretisation as shown in Fig. 2. In Eq. (7) $F_{y,i}(a)$ and $F_{y,i+1}(a)$ are denoting nodal point forces at the positions i and $i+1$, respectively and $\Delta u_{y,i-2}(a+\Delta a)$ and $\Delta u_{y,i-1}(a+\Delta a)$ are the relative nodal point displacements of corresponding nodal points at the positions $i-2$ and $i-1$, respectively. It has been shown in /7,10,11/ that Eq. (7) is holding for finite crack extensions

$\Delta a \gg 0$ and furthermore is numerically exact for the actual FE-discretisation under consideration. By the notation $G(a+\Delta a/2)$ it is emphasized that the obtained energy release rate has the meaning of a mean value for a finite crack extension $\Delta a \gg 0$ and therefore has to be correlated to $a+\Delta a/2$. From Eq. (7) it is evident that the crack closure integral method has the disadvantage of requiring two calculations with different crack lengths a and $a+\Delta a$ for one value $G(a+\Delta a/2)$. Therefore it also will be referred to as 2C-method. But on the other hand this local energy method -2C has the advantage of covering mixed-mode crack tip conditions too and furthermore of delivering simultaneously the separated energy release rates $G_i(a)$, $i=I, II, III$ in this case.

IMPROVED MODIFIED CRACK CLOSURE INTEGRAL METHOD

In order to avoid the just mentioned disadvantage of the 2C-method BUCHHOLZ et al and KANNINEN /4,7,10,11/ have established the following formula

$$G_I(a) = \frac{1}{t} \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2\Delta a} (F_{y,i}(a) \Delta u_{y,i-2}(a) + F_{y,i+1}(a) \Delta u_{y,i-1}(a)) \quad (8)$$

in combination with the LSE-discretisation of Fig. 2. This improved modified crack closure integral method will also be referred to as L2-method or LSE-formula of 2nd order /7/. From Eq. (8) it is to be seen, that the L2-method is based on the same correlations between the nodal point forces and crack face displacements of the crack tip area as the 2C-method, but in contrast to Eq. (7) only one FE-analysis for the actual crack length a is required. This decisive difference, reducing the numerical effort to be made to one half, is based on an assumption corresponding to that one used by RYBICKI and KANNINEN for their modified crack closure integral method (CSE-formula of 1st order) /12/, given for the fracture analysis with constant strain element (CSE) discretisations of plane crack problems in homogeneous materials. Although for Eq. (8) no finite formulation can be given, it has been shown in /4, 7/ that the L2-method can successfully be applied with finite crack extensions Δa and that it can be generalized for the analysis of more complex problems /10,11/. The following results will verify this too. By the L2-method the obtained energy release rate is correlated to the actual crack length a , due to the symmetry of Eq. (8) with respect to the crack tip position i (Fig. 2). In this context it is interesting, that in order to improve RYBICKI and KANNINEN's original method /12/, DATTAGURU et al independently developed some formulae equivalent to Eq. (8), deriving them from the shape functions and the related stress- and displacement fields of the elements forming the actual crack tip (quadrilateral LSE or isoparametric singular quarter point elements) /13,14/.

COMPOSITE CYLINDER WITH COAXIAL INTERFACE CRACK

Mechanical Tensile Loading

All three methods presented and discussed above have been used for the fracture analysis of the axisymmetric fibre pullout problem due to tensile loading /15/, as shown in Fig.3a-c. The global energy method-EN (Eq. (1)) can directly be applied, whereas the local energy methods 2C and L2 (Eqs. (7), (8)) have to be extended first. Evidently one has to expect that the applied axial load will generate mode II conditions at a circular crack front of an

axially extending interface crack, but due to Poisson's ratio of the fibre a mode I term also may occur.

Fig.3 Boundary conditions for mechanical fibre pullout and thermal debonding (BC-B1, B2, B3 and T)

Using cylinder coordinates r, ϕ, z , with z defining the axis of the concentric fibre/matrix composite cylinder, one can give the following formulae for the 2C-method

$$G_I(a+\Delta a/2) = \frac{1}{2\pi r_f} \frac{1}{2\Delta a} (F_{r,i}(a) \Delta u_{r,i-2}(a+\Delta a) + F_{r,i+1}(a) \Delta u_{r,i-1}(a+\Delta a)), (9)$$

$$G_{II}(a+\Delta a/2) = \frac{1}{2\pi r_f} \frac{1}{2\Delta a} (F_{z,i}(a) \Delta u_{z,i-2}(a+\Delta a) + F_{z,i+1}(a) \Delta u_{z,i-1}(a+\Delta a)), (10)$$

delivering simultaneously the separated energy release rates G_i , $i=I, II$ and the total energy release rate G with

$$G(a) = \sum_i G_i(a), \quad i=I, II \quad \text{or} \quad i=I, II, III \quad (11)$$

Corresponding to Eq. (7) and Fig. 2 in Eqs. (9) and (10) F_r and F_z are denoting the radial and axial components of the nodal point forces and Δu_r and Δu_z are the relative radial and axial nodal point displacements, respectively. Because of the axial symmetry of the problem the thickness t of a plane specimen in Eq. (7) has to be replaced by $2\pi r_f$, the circumference of the interface in which the interface crack is modelled to extend with $\Delta a(z, \phi) = \text{const.}$

For the same reason the FE-discretisation for this problem is based on axisymmetric LS-elements (TRIAX6 in ASKA, Fig.4) and it is a very favourable property of these energy methods that they only require a very moderate refinement adjacent to the fibre/matrix interface in which the interface crack is modelled (Fig. 4). In Fig. 4 the displacement field of the mechanically stressed (mark-M) fibre/matrix composite cylinder, supported as given in Fig. 3a (boundary condition-B1), is given for an advanced fibre pullout situation with $a/H = 0.8$. In Fig. 5 the increase of the total specific potential $\bar{\Pi} = \Pi/2\pi r_f$ is plotted versus crack length. Fig. 6 shows the correlated overall energy release rates GG versus crack length, calculated with the three methods EN, 2C and L2. All GG -graphs are showing a maximum value at crack lengths $a/H = 0.2$ and decreasing values with $a/H > 0.2$, when the applied tensile load is stressing increasingly the fibre alone. Apart from short crack lengths $a/H \leq 0.1$ the results obtained by the different methods are in good agreement. This is remarkably because they differ distinctly in the numerical effort they require.

Fig.4 Displacement field for fibre pullout, BC-B1

Fig.5 Total potential for fibre pullout, BC-B1

The most interesting results from the fracture mechanics point of view are given in Fig. 7. Based on the 2C-method it shows that the fibre pullout is creating evidently a mixed-mode problem, even with a dominating mode I part for short crack lengths. For $a/H > 0.1$ mode I is decreasing, whereas the mode II crack tip conditions are increasing rapidly until they predominate the fracture process completely for $a/H \geq 0.3$. As the interface crack here only separates two dissimilar isotropic materials, this differs from a statement given by WANG / 3 /, expecting such a behavior in general only for the delamination of dissimilar anisotropic media. On the other hand this effect has also been observed experimentally /16/, when during fibre pullout the interface crack started to extend out of the interface into the matrix due to mixed-mode crack front conditions. This is a well known behavior for mixed-mode crack extension in homogeneous materials too / 17 /.

Fig.6 Total energy release rates EN, 2C and L2-method, BC-B1

Fig.7 Energy release rates 2C-method, BC-B1

The next Figs. 8-11 illustrate the strong effect which the actual boundary conditions (BCs) have on the fracture process. All other conditions remain unchanged (specimen, load, FE-discretisation) and only the BCs have been altered as given in Fig. 3a-c from BC-B1 to B2 and B3, modelling a kind of fibre- and fibre/matrix precracks, respectively. Boundary condition B3 corresponds to that one used by GRADIN and BÄCKLUND in their fibre pullout investigation by the aid of a simpler EN-method and a generalized J-integral approach / 8 /. The correlated displacement fields are given in Figs. 8 and 10, showing the influence of the different BCs

within the plane of symmetry ($r, \phi, z=0$) on the specimen's deformation and on the opening of the crack faces for $a/H=0.8$ again. Figures 9 and 11 show for the BCs B2 and B3 a rather similar development of all energy release rates G_1 , G_2 and G_G with increasing crack length, but it should be noticed that they differ by about one order in magnitude. In both cases again mixed-mode conditions arise with dominating mode I parts up to crack lengths $a/H \leq 0.2$ (BC-B2, Fig.9) and $a/H \leq 0.3$ (BC-B3, Fig.11), respectively. But in contrast to Fig.7 (BC-B1) here we find monotonously growing mode II conditions with a higher rate for BC-B3 in Fig.11. The development of the total energy release rate G_G is corresponding to the result given /8/, but there the mixed-mode character of this problem has been ignored.

Fig.8 Displacement field for fibre pullout, BC-B2

Fig.9 Energy release rates 2C-method, BC-B2

Fig.10 Displacement field for fibre pullout, BC-B3

Fig.11 Energy release rates 2C-method, BC-B3

Thermal Loading

Composite materials often are not only subjected to extreme mechanical but also to high thermal loads. Therefore the fibre/matrix composite cylinder is now subjected to a stationary and homogeneous temperature rise $\Delta T=100^\circ\text{C}$ and different thermally induced fibre/matrix debonding processes (mark-T) are investigated. Corresponding to the fibre pullout we start considering axial crack extension with the BC-T (Fig.3d). Due to the different thermoelastic material parameters of fibre and matrix (Table 1) an inhomogeneous

geneous stress field is ensued by $\Delta T = \text{const.}$ Evidently it generates mixed-mode conditions for any crack extending in the cylindrical interface between the two dissimilar isotropic materials.

Fig.12 Displacement field for fibre debonding, BC-T

Fig.13 Elastic strain energy for fibre debonding, BC-T

For the same FE-discretisation of the composite cylinder as used before, Fig.12 shows the thermal expansion of the SiC-fibre and the Al-matrix for $\Delta T = +100^\circ\text{C}$ and $a/H = 0.8$. The wide crack opening is indicating a strong mode I part at the circular crack front for this crack length. In Fig.13 the thermally induced specific elastic strain energy $\bar{U} = U/2\pi r_f$ is plotted as it decreases with axial crack extension from a maximum value for $a/H = 0$ (perfectly bonded composite cylinder) to a small residual value U_{res} ($a = H$) for $a/H = 1$. This value remains because the FE-model of the composite cylinder is still connected at a circular interface line at $z = 0$, even for the crack length $a = H$. As the methods EN, 2C and L2 would deliver singular values for G for changes of U with $\Delta a = 0$ (release of the last nodal point conjunctions), this last step can not be included in the analysis. The correlated total energy release rates are given in Fig.14. For all three methods the results nearly coincide and only for $a/H \leq 0.1$ the rather coarse FE-net at the interface causes some insufficiency with the numerical differentiation involved in the method-EN.

Fig.14 Total energy release rates EN, 2C and L2-method, BC-T

Fig.15 Energy release rates 2C-method, BC-T

Fig.15 illustrates on the basis of method-2C how the mixed-mode conditions vary during the thermally induced debonding process. Here the debonding

starts under a pure mode II condition (due to suppressed small negative G_I -values for $a/H \leq 0.2$), showing then a considerable increase of mode I for longer cracks and a decrease of mode II for $a/H \geq 0.5$. Comparing finally Figs.15 and 7 there is a distinct difference to be noticed in the mixed-mode fracture conditions between the thermally induced debonding process and the mechanically created fibre pullout (both with BC-B1 or BC-T).

COMPOSITE CYLINDER WITH CIRCUMFERENTIAL INTERFACE CRACK

Thermal Loading

Although the mechanically ensued fibre pullout problem and the thermally induced debonding processes are different problems so far, they both are governed by the self-similar extension of the interface crack in axial direction of the composite cylinder. It has been shown by BUCHHOLZ /4,7/ that the improved modified crack closure integral method (L2-method, and so the 2C-method too) can successfully be generalized for the fracture analysis of non-coplanar mixed-mode crack extension in the interface of thermally stresses plane fibre/matrix composite models. Hence an attempt was made to generalize the method further in order to include a finite length in the thickness direction /10/. The result is given by the following formulae

$$G_I(\phi, h_j) = \frac{1}{\Delta h_j} \lim_{\Delta \phi \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2r_f \Delta \phi} (F_{r,i}(\psi) \Delta u_{r,i-2}(\psi) + F_{r,i+1}(\psi) \Delta u_{r,i-1}(\psi)), (12)$$

$$G_{II}(\phi, h_j) = \frac{1}{\Delta h_j} \lim_{\Delta \phi \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2r_f \Delta \phi} (F_{\phi,i}(\psi) \Delta u_{\phi,i-2}(\psi) + F_{\phi,i+1}(\psi) \Delta u_{\phi,i-1}(\psi)), (13)$$

$$G_{III}(\phi, h_j) = \frac{1}{\Delta h_j} \lim_{\Delta \phi \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2r_f \Delta \phi} (F_{z,i}(\psi) \Delta u_{z,i-2}(\psi) + F_{z,i+1}(\psi) \Delta u_{z,i-1}(\psi)), (14)$$

in which ψ stands for the variables $\phi, h_j, \Delta h_j$, with ϕ crack angle, h_j actual level of evaluation and Δh_j correlated height or thickness. The variables Δh_j are corresponding to the thickness t with plane problems. For a 3D-problem they have to be defined first by means of the shape functions of the finite elements under consideration and the principal of virtual work. For the FE-discretisation of the composite cylinder by LS-volume elements (HEXE 27 in ASKA) as shown in Fig.16, the Δh_j can be identified in a straightforward manner. The cylinder is subjected to $\Delta T = \text{const.}$ with plane strain boundary conditions (suppressed freedoms in z-direction) and then it is utilized that in this case the $G_i(\phi, h_j)$, $i=I, II$ must be independent from z or h_j , respectively.

Based on Eqs. (12)-(14) and the FE-net of Fig. 16 the mixed-mode I, II and III fracture analysis is performed for a thermally induced ($\Delta T = +100^\circ\text{C}$) debonding process of fibre and matrix by an interface crack. In this case the crack is modelled extending non-coplanar with a given straight crack front in circumferential direction as shown in Fig.16 for a crack angle $\phi = 90$ degrees. Although the FE-discretisation in the z-direction is rather coarse with two LSEs, it provides the analysis with five discrete levels $z = h_j$ of evaluations (levels containing midside or corner nodes of the LSEs). The left side of the longitudinal section given in Fig.16 illustrates the displacement field of the perfectly bonded composite cylinder due to $\Delta T = 100^\circ\text{C}$, whereas the right side is illustrating the displacements of the thermally debonded cylinder ($\phi = 90$ deg.).

Fig.16 Displacement field for fibre debonding BC-T

Fig.17 Energy release rates $h_j/H=0$, L2-method, BC-T

In the plane of symmetry ($z=0$ or $h_j/H=0$) mode I and II crack tip conditions can easily be recognized by the crack opening and the radial dislocations of the opened crack faces, respectively. These radial dislocations show reduced values at the upper evaluation level with $h_j/H=0.5$, but additional dislocations can be seen in the z -direction for $h_j/H=0.5$ and 1.0 , indicating increasing mode III conditions adjacent to the top surface.

These qualitative results are quantified in Figs.17-19 for $h_j/H=0, 0.5, 1.0$ respectively. Figure 17 shows the developments of the energy release rates $G1$ and $G2$ with increasing crack length ($a=r_f\phi$), indicating a highly mixed-mode fracture process with starting mode I dominance, followed by distinctly higher mode II conditions before both parts vanish with further debonding in circumferential direction. A similar picture is Fig.18 giving for $h_j/H=0.5$, with lower maximum values for $G1$ and $G2$ but an additional $G3$ part (mode III), which shows some stationary behaviour for medium crack lengths. At the top surface of the cylinder ($h_j/H=1.0$) this mode III part predominates the crack tip conditions with nearly vanishing mode I and II energy release rates, respectively, as Fig. 19 illustrates.

Fig.18 Energy release rates $h_j/H=0.5$, L2-method, BC-T

Fig.19 Energy release rates $h_j/H=1$, L2-method, BC-T

The accuracy to these results, obtained by the local energy methods L2 and 2C can be proved in the following way. By Eqs. (4) and (5) the thermally induced elastic strain energy $U(a=0)$ of the perfectly bonded (uncracked) and of the completely debonded composite cylinder $U_{res}(a=1)$ can be calculated, defining

$$U_{ref}(a=0) = U(a=0) - U_{res}(a=1) \quad (15)$$

(In this case too, the numerical analysis delivers $U_{res}(a=1)$ being small but not zero due to a last "singular" axial line of contact between fibre and matrix). By the fact that this quantity of elastic strain energy $U_{ref}(a=0)$ should coincidewith the amount of total energy $\hat{U}(a=1)$, released during debonding from the cylinder to the crack, the relation

$$U_{ref}(a=0) \stackrel{!}{=} \hat{U}(a=1) = t \int_{a=0}^{a=1} G(a) da, \quad t, l = \begin{cases} 2\pi r_f, H & \text{for axial debonding} \\ 2H, r_f \pi & \text{for circumf. debond.} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

is defined. Finally with

$$\Delta_{rel} = \frac{\hat{U}(a=1) - U_{ref}(a=0)}{U_{ref}(a=0)} \quad (17)$$

a quantitative measure for the relative deviation of these quantities can be established. The results for the two thermal fracture processes are given in Table 2

TABLE 2
Accuracy of the numerical results

fracture process	$U(a=0)$ (Nmm)	$U_{res}(a=1)$ (Nmm)	$U_{ref}(a=0)$ (Nmm)	$\hat{U}(a=1)$ (Nmm)	Δ_{rel} (%)	num. method	LSE
axial debonding	253.20	20.79	232.41	227.56	-2.1	2C	TRIAX6
circumf. debond.	255.75	9.07	246.68	243.01	-1.5	L2	HEXE27

For both cases and methods, respectively, the results of Table 2 prove the good accuracy of the applied local energy methods, which is especially true for the L2-method managing this mixed-mode, non-coplanar, 3D-fracture analysis with minimum numerical effort. Finally the $U(a)$ -value can be proved to have an accuracy of -1,1% for the HEXE27-LSE model, compared with the analytical result, which is available for the composite cylinder under plain strain conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

This investigation has shown that with the local energy methods of the crack closure integral (method-2C) and the improved modified crack closure integral (method-L2) two straightforward and effective numerical procedures are available for the fracture analysis of rather general and complex crack problems.

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